

Head Motion Control System Wheel Chair

This paper has been submitted to the department of Electrical & Electronic Engineering of East Delta University (EDU) in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Electrical and Electronic Engineering.

SUBMITTED BY:

NAME	STUDENT ID
MahamudHumayonSikder	181000120E
Raton Kumar Mohanta	181000520E
TituSaha	181000620E
Hemel Dhar	181000720E
Bikash Barua	181000920E

SUPERVISED BY:

Abyad Enan

Lecturer

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering

School of Science, Engineering and Technology

EDU
EAST DELTA
UNIVERSITY

EAST DELTA UNIVERSITY (EDU)

[Fall'2020]

Letter of Transmittal

10th January, 2021

The Supervisor
Department of EEE
East Delta University (EDU)
East Nasirabad, Khulshi, Chattogram.

Subject: Submission of Project report.

Dear Sir,

Please find the enclosed project report entitled “**Head Motion Control System Wheel Chair**”. The study has been carried out in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Electrical & Electronic Engineering.

In carrying out the study, we have followed supervisor’s advice and collected required information from several text books, reference books, web sites and other sources. We think you will find it useful and informative. We would be glad to furnish you further explanations or clarifications if required.

Sincerely yours,

Mahamud Humayon Sikder	ID: 181000120E	
Raton Kumar Mohanta	ID: 181000520E	
Titu Saha	ID: 181000620E	
Hemel Dhar	ID: 181000720E	
Bikash Barua	ID: 181000920E	Bikash Barua

DECLARATION

We do hereby solemnly declare that the work presented in this report entitled “**Head Motion Control System Wheel Chair**” has been carried out by us and has not been previously submitted to any other university, college or organization for an academic qualification, certificate or diploma/degree.

We hereby warrant that the work that has been presented here does not breach any existing copyright. We further undertake to indemnify the university against any loss or damage arising from breach of the foregoing obligations.

Authors

MahamudHumayonSikder	ID: 181000120E	
Raton Kumar Mohanta	ID: 181000520E	
TituSaha	ID: 181000620E	
Hemel Dhar	ID: 181000720E	
Bikash Barua	ID: 181000920E	Bikash Barua

EDU
EAST DELTA
UNIVERSITY

EAST DELTA UNIVERSITY (EDU)

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the report entitled is “**Head Motion Control System Wheel Chair**” the valid record of the work done by MahamudHumayonSikder, Raton Kumar Mohanta, TituSaha, Hemel Dhar and Bikash Barua for partial fulfillment of the requirement of the degree of B.Sc. in Electrical and Electronic Engineering (EEE) from **East Delta University (EDU)**.

This work has been carried out under my guidance and is a bonafide record of valid works carried out successfully.

Faculty Guide

Enan

Abyad Enan

Lecturer

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering
School of Science, Engineering and Technology
EAST DELTA UNIVERSITY(EDU)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to express our greatest gratitude to the people who helped and supported us throughout this work. First and foremost we would like to thank our honorable supervisor **Abyad Enan**, Lecturer, Department of EEE, for giving us enormous support, advices and valued guidance concerning this thesis. We are grateful to **Sayed Al Noman**, honorable Vice-Chairman, East Delta University(EDU) for his comments, encouragement and support. We are grateful to our respected coordinator **Toufiq Ahmed**, Assistant Professor, Department of EEE, Faculty of Engineering, East Delta University(EDU) for kindly agreeing to examine our thesis. Next, we would like to thank our family and friends for their valuable support to complete this thesis. Finally, we would like to express our heartiest gratefulness to Almighty Allah for His heavenly blessings. Without his blessings it would not possible to complete our work successfully.

Thank you all

Authors

MahamudHumayonSikder	ID: 181000120E	
Raton Kumar Mohanta	ID: 181000520E	
TituSaha	ID: 181000620E	
Hemel Dhar	ID: 181000720E	
Bikash Barua	ID: 181000920E	Bikash Barua

ABSTRACT

Abstract According to a research there are about 6 million populations in the world who are paralyzed and needs a wheelchair for their mobility. Earlier the wheel chairs had to be moved and be externally supported by any person. To help overcome this “joystick-controlled wheelchairs” are developed. But in regular use, these joystick-controlled wheelchairs became difficult to use. Especially in the case of paralyzed people, the use of joystick became more difficult due to the hard buttons and unidirectional use of the joysticks. To overcome these problems, we’ve tried to develop a “Head-controlled wheelchair” which can be moved with a slight tilt of the head. This can be used in both head and can be controlled to come to the user from a distance. The current work is implemented with Arduino based devices such as Arduino UNO processors and programmed through Arduino IDE. The project has been completed and tested. It works properly and its performance is satisfactory. In future we will develop many other features with this project.

Keywords: Gyro Sensor mpu6050, Arduino Pro Mini board (for Helmet), Arduino nano board (for wheelchair), 500 rpm DC Gear Motor, Bluetooth Module, Wi-Fi module.

Table of Contents

Letter of Transmittal	II
Declaration	III
Certificate	IV
Acknowledgement	V
Abstract	VI

Chapter 1	Introduction	1-4
1.1	Overview	2
1.2	Literature Review	2-3
1.3	Project Objective	3
1.4	Proposed System	4
1.5	Importance of Head Motion Wheel Chair	4

Chapter 2	System Architecture	5-19
2.1	Methodology	6-7
2.2	Block Diagram of Project	7
2.3	Circuit Diagram	8
2.4	Structure of Head Control Wheel Chair	8
2.5	How the Project works	9
2.6	Arduino NANO	10
2.7	Arduino Pro Mini	11-12
2.8	Gyro Sensor	13-14
2.9	Ultrasonic Sensor	14-15
2.10	Motor Driver L298	16
2.11	Bluetooth Module	17
2.12	Wi-Fi Module	18
2.13	DC Gear Motor	19

Chapter 3	Hardware Analysis	20-49
3.1	Hardware to Software Interface	21-30
3.2	Connecting HC – 05 Bluetooth module to Arduino	30-36
3.3	Gyro Sensor MPU 6050	37-43
3.4	Ultrasonic Sensor HC SR04	43-46
3.5	Program Implementation	47-48
3.6	Chair Monitoring System Using Wi-Fi Module	49

Chapter 4	Project Developed and Result Analysis	50-63
4.1	Hardware Implementation	51-60
4.2	Working Principle	61
4.3	Results	62
4.4	Advantages	63

Chapter 5	Discussion and Conclusion	64-68
5.1	Discussion	65
5.2	Future Scope	65
5.3	Conclusion	66
5.4	References	66-68

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2.1	Block Diagram of the stages Design a Project	6
Figure 2.2	Block Diagram of Main Operation	6
Figure 2.3	System Layout	7
Figure 2.4	Block Diagram of Project	7
Figure 2.5	Circuit connection of the project	8

AUTHORS

MahamudHumayonSikder

Raton Kumar Mohanta

Titu Saha

Hemel Dhar

Bikash Barua

Chapter-1
Introduction

1.1 Overview:

Old citizens or disabled persons become dependent on other members of the family to navigate through their habitat or within residence. A smart wheel chair can be a useful assistant for them. Recent development in the field of robotics, automation, embedded system, artificial intelligence etc. can be combined utilized to design such a wheel chair. It can be controlled wirelessly adopting proper communication system. The chair can be controlled by head gesture as well as head gesture method with directions as needed. The previous development of this kind of wheel chair is using a laptop or PC on the wheel chair. By this development the recent wheel chairs are gesture controlled or voice controlled. But the limitations of this kind of technologies are that the wheel chair is getting too bulky and it is to be controlled only by sitting on it. That's why these types of wheel chairs are not giving satisfactory feedback from the users. The proposed model makes the wheel chair a lot easier to assemble and simple in the use, in addition the cost of manufacturing also gets reduced.

1.2 Literature Review:

- According to research paper, “HAND GESTURE RECOGNITION: A LITERATURE REVIEW”[2], it focuses on human computer interaction. It is a survey of recent hand gesture recognition systems. Key issues of hand gesture recognition system are presented with challenges of gesture system. Review methods of recent postures and gestures recognition system presented as well. Orientation histogram method applied in this have some problems which are; similar gestures might have different orientation histograms and different gestures could have similar orientation histograms, besides that, the proposed method achieved well for any objects that dominate the image even if it is not the hand gesture.
- According to research paper, Titled“IR Sensor-Based Gesture Control Wheelchair” [3] published in IEEE,it works on the principle of gesture recognition by using Infrared Sensors.In this method, IR sensors are used for identifying the simple gestures to control the powered wheelchair to move in any direction. In the proposed prototype system, a gesture pad that includes IR sensors, MCU and power management circuit is designed for gesture recognition and identification and a controller for driving motors is implemented. The main problem that comes with IR is during daylight, its sensitivity

is reduced, and hence causing problem for processing the further programs. And it is difficult to recognise exact gestures using IR sensors.

- In research paper published, entitled, “Electric Powered Wheelchairs”, [4] its aim was to review the concepts and previous work on velocity control, traction control, suspension control, stability control, stair-climbing wheelchairs, and wheelchair navigation. The information gathered in this study is intended to promote awareness of the status of contemporary powered wheelchair control technology and increase the functional mobility of people who use EPWs. But, it has a major disadvantage of cost efficiency. It's quite expensive as compared to normal wheel-chair.
- In an article [5], from Int. Journal of Engineering Research and Applications, aims at gesture control wheelchair using hand movements. According to this article, with hand movements, wheelchair's direction can be changed. But it has disadvantage over paralysed patients, who cannot move their hands.
- We are using accelerometer, mounted to the ear piece, so that with movement in head, or say, by moving your head, slightly in different direction, we can move the direction of wheel-chair.

1.3 Project Objective:

The objective of this study is to provide the physically disabled patients who had suffered from losing their extremities due to the accident, age or disease, with an easily controllable wheelchair. Those patients cannot use the manual wheelchair or electric wheelchair with joysticks due to their handicap. The movements of this wheelchair are controlled by head motions with the use of gyroscope sensor. The microcontroller is also used and it is programmed to make the wheelchair moves according to the corresponding motion from the patient's head. Forward movement of the wheelchair due to tilting head forward, left tilt of the user's head will cause the wheelchair to move to the left and so on. An obstacle detection system is done by using ultrasonic sensors. This system showed very good results it will make the usage of this wheelchair safer as compared to standard ones. It will help in enhancing the quality of life for such people and make them less dependent on others. This wheelchair is low cost, provide ease of use and comfortable for the physically disabled patients.

1.4 Proposed System:

Proposes a system in which the wheelchair moves towards left, right, forward and backward direction with respect to the motion of head.

1.5 Importance of Head motion Wheel Chair

- To help the quadriplegic patients to move independently from one place to another with the help of wheel chair by tilt movement of their heads.
- To alert family members in time of emergencies.
- Avoiding obstacles like edges or staircase.
- Enable young disable children and their families to enjoy ordinary lives.
- Increase the number of disable people in employment.

Chapter-2
SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

2.1 Methodology:

Methodology to accomplish any project may involves the steps are shown in the following block diagram. Methodology of this prototype **Head Motion Control System Wheel Chair** mainly classified into two categories. First one is simulation operation and second one is hardware operation. At first we observe the simulation output then making decision for hardware implement.

Fig.2.1 Block diagram of the stages design a project.

Fig.2.2 Block Diagram of Main Operation

Fig.2.3 System Layout

2.2 Block Diagram of Project

Figure2.4: Block diagram of Project

2.3 Circuit Diagram

Fig 2.5: Circuit Connection of the Project

2.4 Structure of Head Control Wheelchair

1. ARDUINO NANO
2. ARDUINO PRO MINI
3. GYRO Sensor- MPU6050
4. Motor Driver (L298)
5. ULTRASONIC Sensor (SR-04)
6. 4WD Car (Demo- Wheelchair)
7. Battery
8. Bluetooth Module
9. Wi-Fi Module
10. DC Gear Motor

2.5 How the Project works

In this work head gesture based wheelchair is designed with ATmega328 microcontroller by using accelerometer. The direction of the wheelchair is observed through Gyro Sensor with the help of Arduino Board. The wheel chair basically takes the input signals from person head gestures and values are sending on Arduino Uno board.

In the present work, the head gestures represent a small movement of head made in different directions. An accelerometer sensor is used to detect different head gestures. In the present work MPU6050 is used as accelerometer sensor. The sensor can be either fixed directly with the heads of the person or can wear with helmet. The accelerometer supports three analog inputs and need to be converting into digital signal using ADC converter to make the analog signal output compatible with microcontroller. The analog to digital conversion is done with the help of ADC module embedded in ATmega328 microcontroller. Based on the ADC readings which are proportional to the accelerometer sensor, the ATmega328 will recognize and decode different gestures of the head. Once the decode of head gesture is mapped into machine understandable code, the microcontroller will process the signal.

Then the Arduino nano board sends signal to DC motor driver in order to control the movement and direction of the wheelchair in required direction. The head gestures are sensed and converted into displacement of the wheelchair in different direction such as left, right, forward, backward directions and stop whenever it is required.

2.6 Arduino Nano

Features:

1. It has 22 input/output pins in total.
2. 14 of these pins are digital pins.
3. Arduino Nano has 8 analog pins.
4. It has 6 PWM pins among the digital pins.
5. It has a crystal oscillator of 16MHz.
6. It's operating voltage varies from 5V to 12V.
7. It also supports different ways of communication, which are:
 - Serial Protocol.
 - I2C Protocol.
 - SPI Protocol.
8. It also has a mini USB Pin which is used to upload code.
9. It also has a Reset button on it.

2.7 Arduino Pro Mini

Features:

- Arduino Pro Mini is a microcontroller board developed by Arduino.cc and comes with Atmega328 microcontroller incorporated inside the board.
- This board comes with 14 digital I/O out of which 6 pins are used for providing PWM output. There are 8 analog pins available on the board.
- It is very small as compared to Arduino Uno i.e. 1/6 of the total size of the Arduino Uno.
- There is only one voltage regulator incorporated on the board i.e 3.3V or 5V based on the version of the board.
- The Pro Mini runs at 8 MHz for the 3.3V version which is half than Arduino Uno board that runs at 16MHz.
- There is no USB port available on the board and it also lacks built-in programmer.

- The labeling on the regulator defines the version of the board i.e. KB33 represents 3.3V edition and KB50 represents 5V edition. However, the board version can also be indicated by measuring the voltage between Vcc and GND pin.
- This board doesn't come with built-in connectors that give you the flexibility to solder the connector in any way you can, based on the requirements and space available for your project.
- Like other Arduino boards, Arduino Pro Mini is open source i.e. you can modify and use the board according to your requirements as all the data and support related to this board is readily available.
- Overcurrent protection ability is another feature that makes this device safe to use in the applications where passing current can affect the overall performance of the project.
- It comes with a flash memory of 32KB out of which 0.5 is used for a bootloader. The flash memory is used for storing the code of the board. It is a non-volatile memory and stores information even if the connection with voltage supply is lost.
- SRAM is a Static Random Access Memory which is 2KB. RAM memory is highly volatile in nature and mainly depends on the constant source of power supply.
- EEPROM comes with a memory of 1KB. It is a read-only memory (ROM) which can be erased and reprogrammed. This memory can be erased by using higher than normal electrical signals.
- The Arduino Software called IDE (Integrated development environment) is used to program the board. The code we write to program the board is called a sketch.

- Like other boards available in the market, Arduino Pro Mini also comes with built-in LED which will blink as we compile and run the relevant program on the board

2.8 Gyro Sensor

Features of Gyro Sensor (mpu6050)

- The triple-axis MEMS gyroscope in the MPU-60X0 includes a wide range of features:
- Digital-output X-, Y-, and Z-Axis angular rate sensors (gyroscopes) with a user-programmable full-scale range of ± 250 , ± 500 , ± 1000 , and $\pm 2000^\circ/\text{sec}$
- External sync signal connected to the FSYNC pin supports image, video and GPS synchronization
- Integrated 16-bit ADCs enable simultaneous sampling of gyros
- Enhanced bias and sensitivity temperature stability reduces the need for user calibration
- Improved low-frequency noise performance
- Digitally-programmable low-pass filter
- Gyroscope operating current: 3.6mA
- Standby current: 5 μ A
- Factory calibrated sensitivity scale factor
- User self-test

Accelerometer Features:

- The triple-axis MEMS accelerometer in MPU-60X0 includes a wide range of features:

- Digital-output triple-axis accelerometer with a programmable full scale range of $\pm 2g$, $\pm 4g$, $\pm 8g$ and $\pm 16g$
- Integrated 16-bit ADCs enable simultaneous sampling of accelerometers while requiring no external multiplexer
- Accelerometer normal operating current: $500\mu A$
- Low power accelerometer mode current: $10\mu A$ at 1.25Hz, $20\mu A$ at 5Hz, $60\mu A$ at 20Hz, $110\mu A$ at 40Hz
- Orientation detection and signaling
- Tap detection
- User-programmable interrupts
- High-G interrupt
- User self-test

2.9 Ultrasonic Sensor

Ultrasonic ranging module HC - SR04 provides 2cm - 400cm non-contact measurement function, the ranging accuracy can reach to 3mm. The modules includes ultrasonic transmitters, receiver and control circuit. The basic principle of work:

- (1) Using IO trigger for at least 10us high level signal,
- (2) The Module automatically sends eight 40 kHz and detect whether there is a pulse signal back.
- (3) If the signal back, through high level , time of high output IO duration is the time from sending ultrasonic to returning.
- (4) Test distance = high level time x velocity of sound (340m/s) / 2,

Wire connecting direct as following:

- 5V Supply
- Trigger Pulse Input
- Echo Pulse Output
- 0V Ground

Electric Parameter

Working Voltage	DC 5 V
Working Current	15mA
Working Frequency	40Hz
Max Range	4m
Min Range	2cm
Measuring Angle	15 degree
Trigger Input Signal	10uS TTL pulse
Echo Output Signal	Input TTL lever signal and the range in proportion
Dimension	45*20*15mm

2.10 Motor Driver L298

This dual bidirectional motor driver is based on the very popular L298 Dual H-Bridge Motor Driver Integrated Circuit. The circuit will allow you to easily and independently control two motors of up to 2A each in both directions. It is ideal for robotic applications and well suited for connection to a microcontroller requiring just a couple of control lines per motor. It can also be interfaced with simple manual switches, TTL logic gates, relays, etc. This board equipped with power LED indicators, on-board +5V regulator and protection diodes.

Features:

- Input Voltage: 3.2V~40Vdc.
- Driver: L298N Dual H Bridge DC Motor Driver
- Power Supply: DC 5 V - 35 V
- Peak current: 2 Amp
- Operating current range: 0 ~ 36mA
- Control signal input voltage range :
- Low: $-0.3V \leq V_{in} \leq 1.5V$.
- High: $2.3V \leq V_{in} \leq V_{ss}$.
- Enable signal input voltage range :
 - o Low: $-0.3 \leq V_{in} \leq 1.5V$ (control signal is invalid).
 - o High: $2.3V \leq V_{in} \leq V_{ss}$ (control signal active).
- Maximum power consumption: 20W (when the temperature $T = 75\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$).
- Storage temperature: $-25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \sim +130\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

- On-board +5V regulated Output supply (supply to controller board i.e. Arduino).

2.11 Bluetooth Module

- Serial Bluetooth module for Arduino and other microcontrollers
- Operating Voltage: 4V to 6V (Typically +5V)
- Operating Current: 30mA
- Range: <100m
- Works with Serial communication (USART) and TTL compatible
- Follows IEEE 802.15.1 standardized protocol
- Uses Frequency-Hopping Spread spectrum (FHSS)
- Can operate in Master, Slave or Master/Slave mode
- Can be easily interfaced with Laptop or Mobile phones with Bluetooth
- Supported baud rate: 9600,19200,38400,57600,115200,230400,460800.

2.12 Wi-Fi Module

Features

- 802.11 b/g/n protocol
- Wi-Fi Direct (P2P), soft-AP
- Integrated TCP/IP protocol stack
- Integrated TR switch, balun, LNA, power amplifier and matching network
- Integrated PLL, regulators, and power management units
- +19.5dBm output power in 802.11b mode
- Integrated temperature sensor
- Supports antenna diversity
- Power down leakage current of < 10uA
- Integrated low power 32-bit CPU could be used as application processor
- SDIO 2.0, SPI, UART
- STBC, 1×1 MIMO, 2×1 MIMO

- A-MPDU & A-MSDU aggregation & s guard interval $\mu 0.4$
- Wake up and transmit packets in $< 2\text{ms}$
- Standby power consumption of $< 1.0\text{mW}$ (DTIM3)

2.13 DC Gear Motor

Features

- 500 RPM 12V DC motors with Metal Gearbox and Metal Gears.
- 25GA
- 6mm Dia shaft with M3 thread hole.
- Length 63 mm without shaft.
- Shaft length 30mm.
- 275gm weight.
- 20 kg cm torque.
- No-load current = 0.15 mA, Load current = upto 4 A(Max).

Chapter-3
Hardware Analysis

3.1 Hardware to Software Interface

Install ESP8266 Add-on in Arduino NANO

To install the ESP8266 board we have to follow these next instructions:

1. In Arduino, go to **File**> **Preferences**

2. Enter **http://arduino.esp8266.com/stable/package_esp8266com_index.json** into the “Additional Boards Manager URLs” field as shown in the figure below. Then, click the “OK” button:

Note: if you already have the ESP32 boards URL, you can separate the URLs with a comma as follows:

https://dl.espressif.com/dl/package_esp32_index.json,

http://arduino.esp8266.com/stable/package_esp8266com_index.json

3. Open the Boards Manager. Go to **Tools > Board > Boards Manager...**

4. Search for **ESP8266** and press install button for the “**ESP8266 by ESP8266 Community**”:

5. That's it. It should be installed after a few seconds.

Testing the Installation

To test the ESP8266 add-on installation, let's see if we can blink an LED with the ESP8266 using the Arduino programming language.

Parts Required

Here's the hardware that you need to complete this project:

- ESP8266
- LED
- 330 Ohm resistor
- Breadboard
- Jumper wires

If you're using an ESP8266-01, you also need an FTDI programmer to upload code.

Uploading the Sketch

Uploading the Sketch to the ESP-12E

If you're using an ESP-12E NodeMCU Kit, uploading the sketch is very simple, since it has built-in programmer. Plug your board to your computer. Make sure you have the right board selected:

We also need to select the Port:

Then, we should copy the code provided:

```
/*  
Rui Santos  
Complete project details at https://randomnerdtutorials.com  
*/  
  
int pin =2;  
  
voidsetup(){  
// initialize GPIO 2 as an output.  
pinMode(pin, OUTPUT);  
}  
  
// the loop function runs over and over again forever  
voidloop(){  
digitalWrite(pin, HIGH);// turn the LED on (HIGH is the voltage level)  
delay(1000);// wait for a second  
digitalWrite(pin, LOW);// turn the LED off by making the voltage LOW  
delay(1000);// wait for a second  
}
```

Click the “Upload” button in the Arduino IDE and wait a few seconds until see the message “Done uploading.” in the bottom left corner.

Uploading the Sketch to the ESP-01

Uploading code to the ESP-01 requires establishing a serial communication between your ESP8266 and a FTDI Programmer as shown in the schematic diagram below.

The following table shows the connections you need to make between the ESP8266 and the FTDI programmer.

ESP8266	FTDI programmer
RX	TX
TX	RX
CH_PD	3.3V
GPIO 0	GND
VCC	3.3V
GND	GND

Then, we just need to connect the FTDI programmer to computer, and upload the sketch to ESP8266 board. We should see the “Done Uploading” message after a few seconds.

Schematic

If we use an ESP8266-12E

Connect an LED to your ESP8266, as shown in the following schematic diagram. The LED should be connected to GPIO 2 (D4).

If we are using an ESP8266-01

If we are using the ESP8266-01 assemble the following circuit.

If everything went well, LED should be blinking every 1 second.

Troubleshooting

If we try to upload a new sketch to your ESP8266 and you get this error message “*esptool.FatalError: Failed to connect to ESP8266: Timed out waiting for packet header*“. It means that your ESP8266 is not in flashing/uploading mode.

Having the right board name and COM port selected, follow these steps:

- Hold-down the “**BOOT/FLASH**” button in your ESP8266 development board
- Press the “**Upload**” button in the Arduino IDE to upload your sketch:
- When you see the “**Connecting....**” message in your Arduino IDE, release the finger from the “**BOOT/FLASH**” button
- After that, you should see the “**Done uploading**” message

Our ESP8266 should have the new sketch running. Press the “**ENABLE/RESET**” button to restart the ESP8266 and run the new uploaded sketch.

Wrapping Up

This is a quick guide that illustrates how to prepare Arduino IDE for the ESP8266 on a Windows PC, Mac OS X, or Linux computer.

That's it, we are ready to start building projects with the ESP8266!

3.2 Connecting HC-05 Bluetooth Module to Arduino

The HC-05 Bluetooth module is an excellent interface for communicating with our mobile. It has a great data transfer rate and very easy to implement.

In order to try this tutorial:

- Any Arduino board
- Grab a breadboard similar to any one of these
- HC-05 Bluetooth Modules
- 2 Resistors, 2K Ohm and 4.6K Ohm
- Dupont jumper wires

Get 2 dupont jumper cables, connect 1 at the rail start and one at the rail end. Now grab your voltmeter and set it on Ohm or connectivity measuring mode then connect the tips to the end of the jumper cables. Make sure that the rail is consistent.

Step 2: If Breadboard's Power Rail Connectivity is continuous we can skip this step

If the power rail connectivity is not consistent then consider using jumper wires to fix that.

Step 3: Arduino Nano Connection

Connect the Arduino Nano and connect its 5V out and GND to power rails as depicted in the image above.

Step 4: Connect the HC-05 Bluetooth Module

Now let's connect the HC-05 and its power sockets. Vcc to the Arduino 5V and GND to Arduino GND.

Step 5: Connect the Bluetooth Module TxD

Next we will connect the HC-05 TXD (this is the pin where all data received from the mobile will be transmitted via it to Arduino) to Arduino pin D3.

Step 6: Connect the Bluetooth Rx/D Module Using the Voltage Divider

Now we will have to connect the HC-05 RXD. First we need to establish a voltage divider using the 2K and the 4.6K ohm resistors. First connect one end of the 2K resistor to Arduino D2 pin, the connect the other end to any unused line in the breadboard, then into this line connect the 4.6K resistor and the other end to the GND.

Connect a dupont jumper originating from the centre point between the 2 resistor and connect it to the HC-05 RXD.

Step 7: Create the Arduino Sketch

Let's move to programming. Grab USB cable and connect the Arduino to laptop and use the code below:

```
#include <SoftwareSerial.h>

// Define the data transmit/receive pins in Arduino

#define TxD 2

#define RxD 3

SoftwareSerial mySerial(RxD, TxD); // RX, TX for Bluetooth

void setup() {

mySerial.begin(9600); // For Bluetooth

Serial.begin(9600); // For the IDE monitor Tools -> Serial Monitor

// Any code that you want to run once....

}

void loop() {

// put your main code here, to run repeatedly:

boolean isValidInput; do { byte c; // get the next character from the bluetooth serial port

while ( !mySerial.available() ); // LOOP...

c = mySerial.read(); // Execute the option based on the character received

Serial.print(c); // Print the character received to the IDE serial monitor

switch ( c ) {

case 'a': // You've entered a

// Do the code you need when 'a' is received.....

mySerial.println( "You've entered an 'a'" );

isValidInput = true;

break;

case 'b': // You've entered b

// Do the code you need when 'a' is received.....
```

```
mySerial.println( "You've entered an 'b'" );  
  
isValidInput = true;  
  
break;  
  
default:  
  
// Do the code you need when any other character is received.....  
  
mySerial.println( "Please enter 'a' or 'b'" );  
  
isValidInput = false;  
  
break;  
  
}  
  
} while ( isValidInput == true ); // Repeat the loop  
  
}
```

3.3 Gyro Sensor MPU 6050

The MPU 6050 communicates with the Arduino through the I2C protocol. The MPU 6050 is connected to Arduino as shown in the following diagram. Next, the GND of the Arduino is connected to the GND of the MPU 6050.

Arduino MPU 6050 connections

The program we will be running here also takes advantage of the Arduino's interrupt pin. Connect your Arduino's digital pin 2 (interrupt pin 0) to the pin labeled as INT on the MPU 6050.

Next, we need to set up the I2C lines. To do this, connect the pin labeled SDA on the MPU 6050 to the Arduino's analog pin 4 (SDA), and the pin labeled as SCL on the MPU 6050 to the Arduino's analog pin 5 (SCL). That's it! You have finished wiring up the Arduino MPU 6050.

Uploading the Code and Testing the Arduino MPU 6050

To test the Arduino MPU 6050, first download the Arduino library for MPU 6050, developed by Jeff Rowberg. Next, unzip/extract this library, take the folder named "MPU6050", and paste

it inside the Arduino's "library" folder. To do this, go to the location where you have installed Arduino (Arduino --> libraries) and paste it inside the libraries folder.

After done this correctly, open the Arduino IDE, we can see "MPU6050" in File --> Examples. Next, open the example program from File --> Examples --> MPU6050 --> Examples --> MPU6050_DMP6.

Arduino MPU 6050 DMP code

Next, we have to upload this code to Arduino. After uploading the code, open up the serial monitor and set the baud rate as 115200. Next, check "Initializing I2C devices ..." on the serial monitor. Now, we see a line saying, "Send any character to begin DMP programming and demo." Just type in any character on the serial monitor and send it, and we start seeing the yaw, pitch, and roll values coming in from the MPU 6050.

The screenshot shows a serial monitor window titled "/dev/ttyUSB0". The output text is as follows:

```
Initializing I2C devices...
Testing device connections...
MPU6050 connection successful

Send any character to begin DMP programming and demo:
Initializing DMP...
Enabling DMP...
Enabling interrupt detection (Arduino external interrupt 0)...
DMP ready! Waiting for first interrupt...
ypr  47.10  50.21  -39.67
ypr  47.03  50.18  -39.69
ypr  46.84  50.12  -39.74
ypr  46.66  50.07  -39.77
ypr  46.51  50.05  -39.78
ypr  46.38  50.03  -39.79
ypr  46.25  50.02  -39.79
ypr  46.09  49.98  -39.81
ypr  45.91  49.92  -39.86
ypr  45.74  49.87  -39.90
ypr  45.58  49.83  -39.92
ypr  45.45  49.80  -39.93
ypr  45.32  49.79  -39.94
ypr  45.19  49.76  -39.95
```

At the bottom of the window, there are controls: a checked "Autoscroll" checkbox, a "No line ending" dropdown menu, and a "115200 baud" dropdown menu.

Arduino MPU 6050 Serial Monitor

DMP stands for Digital Motion Processing. The MPU 6050 has a built-in motion processor. It processes the values from the accelerometer and gyroscope to give us accurate 3D values.

Also, we will need to wait about 10 seconds before we get accurate values from the Arduino MPU 6050, after which the values will begin to stabilize.

Modeling the Values from the Arduino MPU 6050 in 3D Using Processing (Optional)

To view the 3D representation of the data from the MPU 6050, you need to install the processing software. Processing is similar to Arduino, except for a couple of functions. Processing is mainly used for visualizing data and rendering it in 2D/3D models.

Arduino MPU 6050 with Processing

After installing the processing IDE, we will need to download a library called "Toxi". This library is necessary for our Arduino MPU 6050 processing example. Next, extract this file and paste the folder named "toxiclibs-complete-0020" in the "libraries" folder's directory of processing. We can find the "libraries" folder inside the Sketchbook folder for processing.

To visualize the 3D model in processing, first we have to upload the Arduino code for MPU 6050 (MPU6050_DMP6). Before doing that, we need to comment the line in the Arduino MPU6050_DMP6 code that says ...

```
#define OUTPUT_READABLE_YAWPITCHROLL by //#define
OUTPUT_READABLE_YAWPITCHROLL"
```

And uncomment the line that says ...

```
///define OUTPUT_TEAPOT by #define OUTPUT_TEAPOT".
```

Next, we have to open the processing example for the MPU 6050. Open processing, then File --> Open, then navigate to the folder where you installed the MPU6050 library for Arduino. We can find the processing example in MPU6050 --> Examples --> MPU6050_DMP6 --> Processing -->MPUTEapot.

In this code, we have to then check the serial port that is defined in it. By default the line that defines it for LinuxMmac users is ...

```
String portName = "/dev/ttyUSB1";
```

We need to change ttyUSB1 to the port where Arduino is connected.


```
MPUTeapot | Processing 2.0b8
File Edit Sketch Tools Help
MPUTeapot S
gfx = new ToxiclibsSupport(this);
// setup lights and antialiasing
lights();
smooth();
// display serial port list for debugging/clarity
println(Serial.list());
// get the first available port (use EITHER this OR the specific port code below)
String portName = "/dev/ttyUSB0";
// get a specific serial port (use EITHER this OR the first-available code above)
//String portName = "COM4";
// open the serial port
port = new Serial(this, portName, 115200);
// send single character to trigger DMP init/start
// (expected by MPU6050_DMP6 example Arduino sketch)
port.write('r');
}
void draw() {
  if (millis() - interval > 1000) {
    // resend single character to trigger DMP init/start
    // in case the MPU is halted/reset while applet is running
    port.write('r');
  }
}
Experimental: JNI_OnLoad called.
60
```

Editing the Processing file for the MPU 6050

For Windows users, we need to comment the line that says ...

`String portName = "/dev/ttyUSB1";` by `//String portName = "/dev/ttyUSB1";`;

And uncomment the line that says ...

`//String portName = "COM4";` by `String portName = "COM4";`;

And replace "COM4" with the COM port where Arduino is connected (check this by going into Arduino and Tools --> Serial Port).

Now we can test the whole setup. First, upload the Arduino code (MPU6050_DMP6) through Arduino and remember NOT to open the serial monitor. Next, run the processing code

(MPU6050) by pressing the button with the "play" symbol. We will see a small, plane-like object. Wait for about 10 seconds for the MPU 6050 values to stabilize. After that, we can see the 3D model of MPU 6050, which moves in accordance with the sensor.

3.4 Ultrasonic Sensor HC – SR04

The HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensor uses SONAR to determine the distance of an object just like the bats do. It offers excellent non-contact range detection with high accuracy and stable readings in an easy-to-use package from 2 cm to 400 cm or 1” to 13 feet.

The operation is not affected by sunlight or black material, although acoustically, soft materials like cloth can be difficult to detect. It comes complete with ultrasonic transmitter and receiver module.

Technical Specifications

- Power Supply – +5V DC
- Quiescent Current – <2mA
- Working Current – 15mA
- Effectual Angle – <15°
- Ranging Distance – 2cm – 400 cm/1" – 13ft
- Resolution – 0.3 cm
- Measuring Angle – 30 degree

Components Required

We will need the following components –

- 1 × Breadboard
- 1 × Arduino Uno R3
- 1 × ULTRASONIC Sensor (HC-SR04)

Procedure

Sketch

Open the Arduino IDE software. Coding in the Arduino language will control circuit. We Open a new sketch File by clicking New.

Arduino Code

```
const int pingPin=7;// Trigger Pin of Ultrasonic Sensor
const int echoPin=6;// Echo Pin of Ultrasonic Sensor

void setup(){
  Serial.begin(9600);// Starting Serial Terminal
}

void loop(){
  long duration, inches, cm;
  pinMode(pingPin, OUTPUT);
  digitalWrite(pingPin, LOW);
  delayMicroseconds(2);
  digitalWrite(pingPin, HIGH);
  delayMicroseconds(10);
  digitalWrite(pingPin, LOW);
  pinMode(echoPin, INPUT);
  duration =pulseIn(echoPin, HIGH);
  inches =microsecondsToInches(duration);
  cm =microsecondsToCentimeters(duration);
  Serial.print(inches);
  Serial.print("in, ");
```

```
Serial.print(cm);  
Serial.print("cm");  
Serial.println();  
delay(100);  
}  
  
longmicrosecondsToInches(long microseconds){  
return microseconds /74/2;  
}  
  
longmicrosecondsToCentimeters(long microseconds){  
return microseconds /29/2;  
}
```

Code to Note

The Ultrasonic sensor has four terminals - +5V, Trigger, Echo, and GND connected as follows

–

- Connect the +5V pin to +5v on your Arduino board.
- Connect Trigger to digital pin 7 on your Arduino board.
- Connect Echo to digital pin 6 on your Arduino board.
- Connect GND with GND on Arduino.

In our program, we have displayed the distance measured by the sensor in inches and cm via the serial port.

3.5 Program Implementation:


```
head_control_wheelchair | Arduino 1.8.9
File Edit Sketch Tools Help

head_control_wheelchair$

#include <Wire.h>
#define DEVICE (0x53) //ADXL345 device address
#define TO_READ (6) //num of bytes we are going to read each time (two bytes for each axis)

byte buff[TO_READ]; //6 bytes buffer for saving data read from the device
char str[512]; //string buffer to transform data before sending it to the serial port

int pos = 0;
int anglex;
int angley;

int m1=11;
int m2=10;
int m3=13;
int m4=12;
void setup()
{
  Wire.begin(); // join i2c bus
  pinMode(m1,OUTPUT);
  pinMode(m2,OUTPUT);
  pinMode(m3,OUTPUT);
  pinMode(m4,OUTPUT);

  digitalWrite(m1, 0);
  digitalWrite(m2, 0);
  digitalWrite(m3, 0);
  digitalWrite(m4, 0);
}
```

The full program code is given below:


```
1588074126575_1588073821862_code (2) - Notepad
File Edit Format View Help

void loop()
{
  int regAddress = 0x32; //first axis-acceleration-data register on the ADXL345
  int x, y, z;

  readFrom(DEVICE, regAddress, TO_READ, buff); //read the acceleration data from the ADXL345

  //each axis reading comes in 10 bit resolution, ie 2 bytes. Least Significant Byte first!!
  //thus we are converting both bytes in to one int
  x = (((int)buff[1]) << 8) | buff[0];
  y = (((int)buff[3]) << 8) | buff[2];
  z = (((int)buff[5]) << 8) | buff[4];

  anglex = x;
  anglex = constrain(anglex, -260, 260);
  angley = y;
  angley = constrain(angley, -260, 260);

  anglex = map(anglex, -260, 260, 0, 100);
  anglex = (anglex/2);
  angley = map(angley, -260, 260, 0, 100);
  Serial.print(anglex);
  Serial.print(" ");
  Serial.println(angley);
  //we send the x y z values as a string to the serial port
  // sprintf(str, "%d %d", x, y);

  //Serial.print(str);
  //Serial.write(10);

  //It appears that delay is needed in order not to clog the port
  delay(200);
  if(anglex >15 && anglex <39 && angley >35 && angley <70 )
  {
    digitalWrite(m1, 0);
    digitalWrite(m2, 0); //S
  }
}
```

[Head Motion Control System Wheel Chair]

```
1588074126575_1588073821862_code (2) - Notepad
File Edit Format View Help
digitalWrite(m3, 0);
digitalWrite(m4, 0);
}

if(anglex >39 )
{
digitalWrite(m1, 0);
digitalWrite(m2, 0); //L
digitalWrite(m3, 0);
digitalWrite(m4, 1);
}

if( angley <35 )
{
digitalWrite(m1, 1);
digitalWrite(m2, 0); //F
digitalWrite(m3, 0);
digitalWrite(m4, 1);
}

if(angley >70 )
{
digitalWrite(m1, 0);
digitalWrite(m2, 1); //B
digitalWrite(m3, 1);
digitalWrite(m4, 0);
}

//----- Functions
//reads num bytes starting from address register on device in to buff array
void readFrom(int device, byte address, int num, byte buff[]) {
Wire.beginTransmission(device); //start transmission to device
Wire.write(address); //sends address to read from
Wire.endTransmission(); //end transmission
}

meet.google.com is sharing your screen and audio. Stop sharing Hide
Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.
10:35 PM
4/28/2020
```

```
1588074126575_1588073821862_code (2) - Notepad
File Edit Format View Help
{
digitalWrite(m1, 1);
digitalWrite(m2, 0); //F
digitalWrite(m3, 0);
digitalWrite(m4, 1);
}

if(angley >70 )
{
digitalWrite(m1, 0);
digitalWrite(m2, 1); //B
digitalWrite(m3, 1);
digitalWrite(m4, 0);
}

//----- Functions
//reads num bytes starting from address register on device in to buff array
void readFrom(int device, byte address, int num, byte buff[]) {
Wire.beginTransmission(device); //start transmission to device
Wire.write(address); //sends address to read from
Wire.endTransmission(); //end transmission

Wire.beginTransmission(device); //start transmission to device
Wire.requestFrom(device, num); // request 6 bytes from device

int i = 0;
while(Wire.available()) //device may send less than requested (abnormal)
{
buff[i] = Wire.read(); // receive a byte
i++;
}
Wire.endTransmission(); //end transmission
}

meet.google.com is sharing your screen and audio. Stop sharing Hide
Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.
10:35 PM
4/28/2020
```

3.6 Chair Monitoring System Using Wi-Fi Module:

Head Motion control system Wheel chair

Mahamud Humayon Sikder .
(181000120E)

Raton Kumar Mohanta .
(181000520E)

Hemel Dhar .(181000720E)

Bikash Barua .(181000920E)

Titu Saha .(181000620E)

C_State= NOT Moving7.812020

Chair Position: NOT Moving

Chair Battery Voltage: 7.81

Front Obstacle? : NO

Back Obstacle? : NO

Figure: Mobile Display

Chapter – 4
Project Developed
&
Result Analysis

4.1 Hardware Implementation

4.2 Working Principle

Motion Detection The major interaction is the head motion detection and wheelchair locomotion. The head motion detection is the steering for the wheelchair. The head motions for navigation are detected by the MPU-6050 sensor and the following data would be sent to Raspberry Pi.

- G_x = Gyro X-axis data in degree/seconds
- G_y = Gyro Y-axis data in degree/seconds
- G_z = Gyro Z-axis data in degree/seconds
- A_x = Accelerometer X-axis data in g
- A_y = Accelerometer Y-axis data in g
- A_z = Accelerometer Z-axis data in g

Transmitter side**Receiver side**

4.3 Results:

The functional operations are implemented in the Arduino IDE software. The description/action of various commands used in the program is shown in table 1. Table 1 reflects the various control functions used to control and movement and direction of the vehicle in desired direction. The functions are developed in such a way that they able to provide more accurate sensitivity and response in moving and direction change. The response time of the functions with respect to the sensors is tested for several times and designed and modified the program in order to achieve good results. The front() and back() functions are developed to control the direction of the vehicle both in forward and backward direction. Similarly, the functional commands left() and right() are developed to the control the direction of the vehicle in right and left direction. The functions reads the input signals from various sensors through analog inputs and sends output to output devices like motors to control the wheels rotation.

Table 1:

Functional Table Head Movement	Function	Action
Forward	front()	Chair moves forward
Backward	back()	Chair moves backward
Left	left()	Chair moves left
Right	right()	Chair moves right
Zero Position	stop()	Chair stops

When chair moves forward and backward, the 4 wheels of the chair will also rotate clockwise and anticlockwise respectively.

When chair turns right side, the 2 wheels of right side will rotate anticlockwise and the 2 wheels of left side will rotate clockwise.

In the case of turning left side, then it will oppose the process.

4.4 Advantages:

- The wheel chair detects the obstacle at the front and back sides both and stop the movement within a range of 1 feet with an alarm.
- Without any external help the paralyzed person can operate his own chair.
- The prototype of the system is successfully developed to move the wheel chair Left, Right, Forward, and Backward directions or stay in the same position.

Chapter-5
DISCUSSION
&
CONCLUSION

5.1 Discussion:

After the completion of our project, Head motion controlled wheelchair for handicapped, we have tested it for various cases and the wheelchair is working successfully for all the conditions. We could easily operate the wheelchair in forward, backward, left or right directions using head motions and stop the wheelchair as and when desired by the user. The wireless module also works well in sending the signals from head motions to the wheelchair chassis in the receiver circuit. However, we could use high range ASF, FSK transmission modules based on 434 MHz frequency for a higher range and accuracy for the operation of the wheelchair. Finally, the complete cost of our wheelchair operated by head tilt movements is coming up to 30,000 TK, that is quite economical as compared to other automatic wheelchairs coming in the market. So, we have made this product cost effective and reliable.

5.2 Future Scope:

- Instead of using acceleration motion optical sensor can be used to detect eye retina to move wheel chair accordingly
- On road driving need multi-dimensional parameter estimation to avoid risks
- Voice command IC's can be used to interface with microcontroller
- The GSM can be embedded in to the present work to extend its feature such as sending messages during emergency
- Research is going on development of handicap wheel chair using nervous system of human
- Addition of solar charged battery.
- Facility to operate on ordinary 6-volt alkaline battery used in EVM's.
- Intelligent indoor navigation.
- Intelligent eye gesture control can be integrated for reading using Raspberry Pi and other technologies.

5.3 Conclusion:

This study proposed a work of a novel smart wheelchair with an obstacle detection system for driving safety. The hardware of the smart wheelchair is based on the gyroscope sensor interfacing with a microcontroller. This system employed the gyrosensor MPU6050 as the main component of the design to control the movements of the wheelchair according to the user's head gestures. Ultrasonic sensors are the obstacle detection system that stops the wheelchair as it reaches to an obstacle. Interfacing all these sensors to the wheelchair was controlled by the microcontroller Atmega328p. The developed system provides a safer environment for the elderly and the disabled; they can travel indoors or even outdoors alone with safety than before.

5.4 REFERENCES:

- [1] R. Barea, L. Boquete, M. Mazo and E. Lopez, "System for assisted mobility using eye movements based on electrooculography," in *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 209-218, Dec. 2002.
- [2] Francois, Alexandre. "Real-Time Multi-Resolution Blob Tracking." Institute for Robotics and Intelligent Systems, University of Southern California (2004).
- [3] J.S. Jin. "Pose determination of human head using one feature point based on head movement", 2004 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo (ICME) (IEEE Cat No 04TH8763) ICME-04, 2004
- [4] National Spinal Cord Injury Statistical Center. "Facts and Figures About SCI." Spinalcord.org. National Spinal Cord Injury Association, 29 July 2007.
- [5] X. Huo, J. Wang and M. Ghovanloo, "Wireless control of powered wheelchairs with tongue motion using tongue drive assistive technology," 2008 30th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society, Vancouver, BC, 2008, pp. 4199-4202.
- [6] Akmeliawati, Rini, Faez S. BaTis, and Umar J. Wani. "Design and development of a hand-glove controlled wheelchair", 2011 4th International Conference on Mechatronics (ICOM), 2011.

- [7]AleksandarPajkanovic,BrankoDokic:”*WheelchairControlbyHeadMotion*”,SerbianJournalo ElectricalEngineering,Vol.10,No.1,February2013,135-151.
- [8]M.B.KumaranandA.P.Renold,”*Implementationofvoicebasedwheelchairfordifferentlyabled*, ”2013FourthInternationalConferenceonComputing,CommunicationsandNetworkingTechnolo gies(ICCNT),Tiruchengode,2013,pp.1-6.
- [9]S.ShaheenandA.Umamakeswari:”*IntelligentWheelchairForPeopleWithDisabilities*”,Intern ationalJournalofEngineeringandTechnology(IJET),5(1),pp.391-397,2013.
- [10]PreetiSrivastava,Dr.S.Chatterjee,RitulaThakur:”*ANovelHeadGestureRecognitionBasedC ontrolforIntelligentWheelchairs*”,Intern ationalJournalofResearchinElectricalandElectronicsEngineeringVolume2,Issue2,April- June,2014,pp.10-17
- [11]Arcoverde, Euclides & M. Duarte, Rafael & M. Barreto, Rafael & Paulo Magalhaes, Joao & C. M. Bastos, Carlos & Ing Ren, Tsang & Cavalcanti, George. (2014). ”*Enhancedreal- timeheadposeestimationsystemformobiledevice*”. Integrated Computer Aided Engineering. 21. 28 1-293. 10.3233/ICA-140462.
- [12]N. Shinde and K. George, ”*Brain- controlled driving aid for electric wheelchairs*” 2016 IEEE 13th International Conference on Wearable and Implantable Body Sensor Networks (BSN), San Francisco, CA, 2016, pp. 115-118.
- [13]Home—BrainAndSpinalCord.org— Brain&SpinalCordInjuryInformation,BrainandSpinalCord.[Online].Available:<http://www.brainandspinalcord.org/>.
- [14]MPU-6050TripleAxisAccelerometerandGyroBreakoutBoard-SparkFunElectronics-SensorsDigiKeyElectronics,Digikey.In.(2018).”<https://www.digikey.in/catalog/en/partgroup/mpu-6050-triple-axis-accelerometer-and-gyro-breakout-board/51939?>”.
- [15]U.HC-SR04,UltrasonicSensor-HC-SR04-SEN-13959-SparkFunElectronics,Sparkfun.Com.(2018).”<https://www.sparkfun.com/products/13959>”.
- [16]Amazon.In.Relay6Channel5V,[image]Availableat:”<https://www.amazon.in/SLB-Works-6-Channel-Optocoupler-Arduino>”(2018).
- [17]TataWiperMotor,2018.[image]”<http://www.industrybuying.com/wiper-motors-lucas-tvs-AU.AU.WI.1420182/>”.
- [18]RaspberryPi.(2018).RaspberryPi3ModelB-RaspberryPi.[online]Availableat:<https://www.raspberrypi.org/products/raspberry-pi-3-model-b/>.

[19]Generationrobots.com.(2018).[online]Availableat:<https://www.generationrobots.com/media/JQC-3FF-v1.pdf>.

[20]Sciencing.com.(2018).[online]Availableat:<https://sciencing.com/1n4007-diode-specs-7448252.html>.

[21]Anon,(2018).[online]Availableat:<https://www.indiamart.com/proddetail/exide-12v-100ah-powersafe-plus-smf-battery-11407755230.html>.

[22]intex.in.(2018).IntexPowerBank11K—

11000mAhPowerBankwithTorch.[online]Availableat:<http://www.intex.in/power-bank-11k>.